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PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGY OF APPLE JUICE CONCENTRATED

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Abstract: Upon acceptance, the quantity and quality of fruits and vegetables are determined, taking an average sample (4-15 kg) for analysis. There are mechanized samplers for selection of tomatoes from the unloading conveyor.

Key words: Storage, washing, drying, processing, product.

Raw material inspection. All fruits are inspected, rejecting substandard (immature, overripe, affected by diseases and pests), as well as impurities. Raw materials are inspected manually at the conveyor, which moves at a speed of not more than 0.1 m/s. The fruits are distributed on the tape evenly in one layer. Roller conveyors are used for inspection, allowing inspection of raw materials from all sides.

Washing. The fruits coming for processing have surface contamination of mineral or organic origin. A significant part of these contaminants is introduced with dust. The surface of the fruits abounds with various microorganisms (epiphytic microflora) that enter from the environment and are carried by insects. During the washing process, mechanical impurities, microorganisms and pesticides remaining after the chemical treatment of plants should be removed from the surface of the fruit. Fruits and vegetables are delivered for processing in containers, boxes or in bulk by road transport and unloaded into a receiving hopper filled with 1/3 water

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(Fig. 1), where heavy impurities (stones, clods of earth, etc.) are removed if they accidentally got into the raw material.

Technological scheme for the production of apple concentrated juice

Splitting up. Benign fruits are served in a grater-knife type, which grinds apples into particles of 2-6 mm. The degree of grinding is adjusted depending on the density of the apples.

Pressing. The main method of extracting fruit juices under industrial conditions is pressing in batch and continuous presses.

When pressed, the pulp is subjected to gradually increasing pressure, which leads to the release of juice. After pressing, waste remains - pomace, which is a mass of fruit pulp that is almost dry to the touch. The loaded platform is brought under the squeezing device and a small pressure hydraulic piston is turned on. The pressure is increased gradually, otherwise the pulp may get into the juice or the burlap may break. When a further increase in pressure is difficult, the second piston is used to supply hydraulic fluid, raise the pressure to 2.5 MPa and hold it for 5 ... 10 minutes until the release of juice stops. Then the platform is rolled back for unloading. The total duration of pressing is 15...20 min. The pomace is unloaded onto the conveyor, which delivers them to the bucket elevator, and the elevator - to the storage bin. The pomace is then taken out of the factory to be fed to livestock or for other purposes. When processing fruits into juice and seeds for nurseries, the juice is squeezed out so as not to cause deformation of the seeds. The specific pressure on the pulp when squeezing juice from apples should be 1.0. .1.2 MPa. In each case, test pressing is carried out.

Filtration. After clarification, a sediment remains in the juice, which is removed by

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passing the juice through filters of various systems or by centrifuge separation. Fruit juices are filtered at constant and low pressure. The sediment contained in the juice, consisting of organic particles, is easily compressed at elevated pressure, which causes filter blocking, preventing further process.

Filtration requires a pressure differential across both sides of the filter wall. With an increase in pressure, the process rate first increases, and then, due to compression and blockage of the filter pores, decreases. The optimal pressure drop is 70 - 80 kPa. For filtering fruit juices, filter presses, pre-wash filters and drum vacuum filters are used.

The filtered juice is allowed to be recirculated until transparent, after which the filtered juice is fed to deaeration.

Enzyme processing. Juice with a temperature of about 35-40°C enters the reserve with a stirrer, where it is processed with pectolic enzymes for 90 minutes.

Ultrafiltration. After processing with enzymes, the juice is filtered using semi-permeable membranes in special apparatus at a pressure of 0.1-0.8 MPa.

Concentration. Concentrated juices are obtained mainly by evaporation, less often by freezing and reverse osmosis with the capture of aromatic substances and their return to the finished product.

a) Concentration by evaporation is carried out in evaporators. The lower the evaporation temperature and the shorter the duration of the operation, the higher the quality of the resulting juice, so it is advisable to carry out the evaporation in vacuum apparatus. Apple juice withstands short-term heating to a temperature of 45 ... 55 °C without noticeable changes in properties.

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b) Freeze concentration is based on cooling the juice below freezing. Part of the water freezes and in the form of crystals is separated from the concentrate by separation. The lower the freezing temperature, the higher the solids content in the finished product. At low temperatures, the juice undergoes minimal changes. The freezing method is used to obtain juice with a solids concentration of 45-50%. Freezing is used to produce concentrated citrus juices.

c) Concentration using membranes - reverse osmosis - improves the quality of the finished product due to the low process temperature. The essence of the method lies in the fact that two liquids with different concentrations of dissolved substances are placed on both sides of the membrane. An osmotic pressure develops at the membrane boundary, and water moves from a solution of low concentration to a solution of high concentration until the concentrations are equal. If pressure is applied to a solution with a high concentration, then water will flow in the opposite direction.

Sterilization. The quality of canned food and the duration of their storage without spoilage depend on how carefully and correctly their sterilization is carried out, under which microorganisms die and conditions are created under which the development of spores of microorganisms stops. The sterilization regime depends on the type of product, size and type of container. In an acidic environment, microorganisms die faster than in a neutral one; canned food with solid products warms up longer than with liquid; tin containers heat up faster than glass containers. In this regard, for each type of canned food, its own sterilization regime has been developed. Sterilization temperature ranges from 140-1600C. Sterilization is carried out in special devices - autoclaves.

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Bottling. Products are packaged in carefully washed containers. At the same time, each jar is filled with a strictly defined amount of products (deviations from the established norm are allowed within 1 ... 2%). The temperature of the juice when pouring into cans with a capacity of 3 liters. is 90-95°C. Packing of products is mechanized. Banks with a capacity of 2000 and 3000 cm³ are filled with a liquid product on an automatic filler. And then seals the jars with the help of special machines.

Storage. Products are stored in well-ventilated warehouses on wooden racks or pallets at a relative humidity of not more than 75%.

Storage temperature of canned vegetables packed in glass and metal jars - from 0 to 25 °C; in polymer packaging of the "bag in a box" type - from 0 to 20 °C, unsterilized products in barrels - from 0 to 12 °C, in aluminum tubes - from 0 to 5 °C; fruit and berry canned products in all types of containers - from 0 to 25 °C; salted and sour vegetables, pickled fruits and berries, boiled, salted and pickled mushrooms in barrels - from minus 1 to 4 °C; canned mushroom products in glass and metal jars - from 0 to 15 °C; fruit, berry and vegetable canned semi-finished products, as well as canned with chemical preservatives in all types of containers - from 0 to 25 °C.

The shelf life of products from the date of production is set in the regulatory document for products of a particular type. Shelf life guaranteeing bacteriological stability is not established.

